

PREVENTION AND ITS MANAGEMENT OF HEART ATTACK BY HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINES

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ABSTRACT

Heart attack is a very serious condition [life threatening]. This condition produces by-mostly in high Cholesterol, Triglycerides, LDL, Stress, sedentary work, faulty diet. High and low Blood pressure, diabetes etc.

INTRODUCTION

A heart attack is a medical emergency. A heart attack usually occurs when a blood clot blocks blood flow to the heart. Without blood, tissue loses oxygen and dies.

BLOOD SUPPLY OF HEART

Mainly two coronary arteries found in heart

1. Right coronary arteries (RCA)
2. Left main coronary arteries (LMCA)

Left main coronary arteries are divided into two types-

1. Left anterior descending arteries (LAD)
2. Left circumflex arteries (LCX)

Each coronary arteries, percentage of blood supply of heart

1. Right coronary arteries [30-40%]
2. Left anterior descending arteries [40-50%]
3. Left circumflex arteries [15-20%]

Coronary arteries 100% blood supply of heart But heart 30% recruitment of blood.

Mainly (70%) blockage, not a serious problem**Why?**

30% blood recruitment – During running, exercise, hard work etc.

20% blood recruitment- During walk.

10% blood recruitment- During rest, and Sleep

Heart attacks caused by

- Atherosclerosis
- Coronary Artery Disease
- Coronary Artery Spasm

Risk Factors

- Smoking
- Poor diet
- Sedentary Life Style
- Obesity
- High Blood Pressure
- High Cholesterol
- High Triglyceride
- Diabetes
- Autoimmune Conditions
- Family History
- Age

General symptoms for a heart attack can include

- Chest pain or discomfort
- Shortness of breath
- Pain in your arm, shoulder or neck
- Nausea
- Sweating
- Dizziness
- Fatigue
- Upper body pain
- Trouble breathing

HOMOEOPATHIC TREATMENT

ACONITUM NAPELLUS

Stitching pain in chest. Palpitation, with anxiety, fainting, and tingling in fingers. Pulse full, hard; tense and bounding; sometimes intermits. Temporal and carotid arteries felt when sitting.^[3]

Feels swelled. Carditis. Palpitation with anxiety, fainting and tingling in fingers, pain down left arm. Heart pain into left shoulder. Heart pain into left shoulder, aggravation sitting erect. Tachycardia. Pulse fast, bounding shaking, forcible and tumultuous or wiry, very irritable. Arterial tension.^[4]

ALLIUM SATIVUM

Has vasodilatory properties. Arterial hypotension begins usually in 30 to 45 minutes after twenty to forty drops doses of the tincture.^[3]

CIMICIFUGA (ACTAEA RACEMISA)

Irregular, slow, trembling pulse. Tremulous action. Angina pectoris. Numbness of left arm; feels as if bound to side. Heart action ceases suddenly, impending suffocation. Left sided infra mammary pain.^[3]

Heart Troubles reflex symptoms of uterus or ovaries. Palpitation from least motion [Digitalis]^[5]

Sore; swelled; or enlarged as if. Needle like pains at heart. Pain spread all over the chest to the back, and down to the left arm which feels numb and as if bound to the side. Pulse weak, irregular, trembling, drops every 3rd, or 4th beat.^[4]

AGARICUS MUSCARIUS

Irregular, tumultuous palpitation, after tobacco. Pulse intermittent and irregular. Cardiac region oppressed, as if thorax were narrowed. Palpitation with redness of face.^[3]

Palpitation, during coition. Pressure or burning sticking, from heart to left scapula. Angina pectoris, with excessive pain only.

Shocks; at heart region, from sudden noise, from eructation or coughing.^[4]

AMYLENUM NITROSUM

Pain and constriction around the heart. Fluttering of heart on least excitement. Tumultuous palpitation. Angina Pectoris with great anxiety. Full soft pulse. aching backward along the left floating rib.^[4]

Rapidly dilates the arteries and accelerates, but later weakens and retards the pulse. Intense surging of blood to face and head. Angina pectoris: Tumultuous heart action; intense throbbing of heart and carotids. Puerperal convulsions immediately after delivery.^[5]

ANTIMONIUM TARTARICUM

Great precordial anxiety, with vomiting of mucus and bile. Palpitation with uncomfortable hot feeling. Paralytic depression of heart. Weak quick pulse. Sensation of coldness in blood vessels. Palpitation with loose stools.^[4]

ARGENTUM NITRICUM

Palpitation; with nausea, aggravation Lying on right side, riding in car; Amelioration Pressing by hand. Unpleasant sensation of fullness about the heart Amelioration Fresh open air. Pulse irregular intermittent. Anxiety, with palpitation and throbbing throughout the whole body.^[4]

AURUM METALLICUM

Sensation as if the stopped beating, immediately followed by hard rebound. Oppression at the heart. Violent palpitation; at puberty. Cardiac hypertrophy. Angina Pectoris. Aortic disease. Carotids and temporal arteries throb visibly. Pulse, rapid, feeble, irregular. High blood pressure. Feels loose on walking. Palpitation compels him to stop. Heart bruised, sore Aggravation Suppressed foot sweat.^[4]

Sensation as if the heart stood still; as though it ceased to beat and then suddenly gave one hard thump (Sep.). Violent palpitation; anxiety, with congestion of blood to head and chest after exertion; pulse small, feeble, rapid, irregular Visible beating of carotid and temporal arteries (Bell., Glon.). Fatty degeneration of heart (Phos.).^[5]

BARYTA CARBONICA

Cardiac symptoms, after suppressed foot sweat or after masturbation.

Heart feels bruised, sore. Palpitation and distress in region of heart lying on left side. Palpitation felt in head. Aneurism. Pulse; slow, small. High blood pressure. Arteriosclerosis.^[4]

BOVISTA LYCOPERDON

Visible palpitation of heart; of old maids. Palpitation as if heart working in water. Palpitation, with tremor of hands, aggravation Bathing, excitement.^[4]

BROMIUM

Hypertrophy; from gymnastics, with palpitation. Cutting pain running upwards, heart disease. violent palpitation aggravation Lying on left side. Nervous palpitation; with nausea; with headache.^[4]

Hypertrophy of heart from: Gymnastics in growing boys (from Calisthenics in young girls, Caust.).^[5]

BUFORANA

Rapid heart action; in exophthalmos. Feels too large. Palpitation; with headache, during menses.^[4]

CACTUS GRANDIFLORUS

Feels Clutched and Released Alternately by an Iron Band, or feels it expand and contract; seems to turn over. Endocarditis, with mitral insufficiency. Palpitation; aggravation. Lying on left side; at the approach of menses; during the day while walking; from disappointed love. Stitches in heart. Endocardial murmurs. Hypertrophy. Low blood pressure. Pulse; irritable, intermittent, feeble. Irregular and intermittent action, after forceps delivery. Heart disease, with oedema of left hand. As if heart would fly to pieces on holding the breath. Pulsations increase on holding the breath. Aneurism of large arteries and heart. Tobacco heart.^[4]

CACTUS GRANDIFLORUS

Heart feels as if clasped and unclasped rapidly by an iron hand: As if bound, “had no room to beat.” Palpitation: Day and night; worse when walking and lying on Left side (Lach.); at approach of menses.^[5]

DIGITALIS PURPUREA

Sudden flushes of heat, followed by great nervous weakness and irregular intermitting pulse, occurring at the climacteric; Aggravation by least motion. Weak heart without valvular complications. Sensation as if heart would stop beating if she moved (Cocaine-fears that unless constantly on the move heart will cease beating, Gels.). Pulse full, irregular, very slow and weak; intermitting every third, fifth or seventh beat. Blueness of skin, eyelids, lips,

tongue; cyanosis. Distended veins on lids, ears, lips and tongue. Fatal syncope may occur when being raised to upright position.^[5]

GELSEMIUM SEMPERVIRENS

Fears that unless on the move heart will cease beating (fears it would cease beating if she moved, Dig.). Slow pulse of old age.^[5]

IODIUM

Palpitation, worse from least exertion (compare Dig., from least mental exertion, Calc-Ars.). Sensation as if the heart was squeezed together; as if grasped with an iron hand (Cact., Sulph.).^[5]

KALMIA LATIFOLIA

In heart diseases that have developed from rheumatism, or alternate with it. Pulse slow, scarcely perceptible (35 or 40 per minute); pale face and cold extremities.^[5]

NAJA TRIPUDIANS

Simple hypertrophy of heart. For restoring a heart damaged by acute inflammation, or from relief of sufferings of chronic hypertrophy and valvular lesions. Irritating, dry, sympathetic cough in the acute stage of rheumatic carditis, or chronic organic lesions (Spong.). Threatened paralysis of heart, post-diphtheritic. Pulse irregular in force, but regular in rhythm. Inability to speak with choking, nervous, chronic palpitation, especially after public speaking; pain < by carriage riding or lying on side. Severe stitching pain in region of heart.^[5]

SCOPARIUS GENISTA

Anxious oppression, radiating to left shoulder and neck. Palpitation with congestion to head. Angina pectoris. Tobacco heart.^[4]

SPIGELIA ANTHELMIA

Rheumatic affections of heart (Kalm., Led., Naja); systolic blowing at apex. Aneurysm. Chest affections with stitching pains synchronous with pulse, Aggravation from motion, Amelioration cold, wet weather. Palpitation: Violent, visible and audible; from least motion; when bending forward; systolic blowing at apex.^[5]

SYPHILINUM

Heart: Lancinating pains from base to apex, at night (from apex to base, Med.; from base to clavicle, or shoulder, Spig.).^[5]

TABACUM

Palpitation: Violent when lying on left side; goes off when turning to the right. Pulse: Quick, full, large; small, intermittent, exceedingly slow; feeble, irregular, almost imperceptible.^[5]

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